

A Constrained Optimization Approach to Virtual Fixtures for Multi-Robot Collaborative Teleoperation

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Abstract—This paper presents a constrained optimization framework that enables the implementation of multi-robot constraints, as virtual fixtures, to assist human operators, in a teleoperated scenario. The collaborative constraints guide the motion of multiple robots such that the spatial and temporal relationships are maintained between them, while following human input motion objectives. We demonstrate this control architecture for the task of manipulating a surgical knot to a target point. The teleoperation system uses four arms from a da Vinci Surgical System[®] (two master manipulators and two slave manipulators), with custom electronics and software. It extends previous work, which focused on a cooperatively controlled system where the motions of two robots were directly controlled by user-applied forces. Our current system enables us to effectively evaluate the accuracy of the knot positioning task and completion time in a clinically realistic setup for Minimally Invasive Surgery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) offers many benefits over conventional open surgery, including reduced trauma and recovery time. Compared to open surgery, robotic assisted MIS presents significant challenges to surgeons in terms of limited dexterity in a constrained workspace, and the loss of haptic feedback and direct visualization. Robotic assisted MIS has undergone tremendous technological innovation over the past decade and can be classified into two categories based on how the pre-operative data is used during the procedure: (1) for the surgical CAD/CAM approach, a robot follows a pre-determined surgical plan and requires minimal surgical intervention, and is suitable for more static environments such as spine surgery or bone machining; (2) for surgical assistant systems, the pre-operative model might not be available or useful (e.g., in soft tissue surgery) and the robot generally requires the surgeon's direct manipulation, decision and/or evaluation during the procedure [1].

Over the last decade, several surgical assistant systems have been developed, including the da Vinci Surgical system[®] from Intuitive Surgical, Inc., and Sensei[®] X Robotic Catheter from Hansen Medical, Inc. In these surgical assistant systems, the surgical procedures are still performed manually by the surgeon; the robotic device merely follows the human commands and offers little automation or assistance capabilities. Some researchers have attempted to automate parts of MIS intervention. Mayer, et al [2] use a supervised machine learning algorithm on knot tying

trajectories recorded during actual trials by surgeons and can generate a semi-automated procedure that can be played back by the robot at a later time, thus allowing automatic task completion.

We support the alternative approach of a *surgeon-in-the-loop* controller that uses intra-operative sensing, e.g., endoscope, ultrasound imaging, and MRI, to generate *virtual fixture* (VF) motion constraints that help the surgeons to perform a task. VF algorithms generate task-dependent motion constraints for a robotic manipulator performing a task by limiting its movement into restricted workspace and/or influencing its motion along a desired path and are classified as *Forbidden Region* (FRVF) or *Guidance* (GVF) virtual fixtures, respectively [3]. Kapoor, et al. have presented a library of task primitives, such as *stay above a plane*, *move along a line*, and *rotate about a point*, that can be combined using different operators to provide assistance for complex surgical tasks [4]. This approach allows for reduction in the cognitive load of the surgeon through active motion assistance while keeping the surgeon in command at all times.

A basic constrained optimization formulation is shown in (1), where $C(X(q + \Delta q), X^d)$ is the objective function associated with the difference between the actual state variable X and the desired state variable X^d . The state, $X = X(q + \Delta q)$ is a function of joint variables q and joint incremental motion Δq . The solution vector Δq^c must satisfy motion constraints in the form of one or more inequalities $A(X(q + \Delta q)) \leq b$. Δq_U and Δq_L are the upper and lower rate limit for Δq . For each control step, the optimization controller computes a desired incremental motion Δq^c , based on constraints and objectives generated from various real-time input sources.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta q^c &= \min_{\Delta q} C(X(q + \Delta q), X^d) \\ \text{s.t. } & A(X(q + \Delta q)) \leq b, \\ & \Delta q_L \leq \Delta q \leq \Delta q_U \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Constrained motion control was extended to tasks using multiple robots in our prior knot manipulation system [5], where two or more robots perform constrained motion tasks in a shared workspace, subject to spatial and temporal relationships present in the environment. For example, a spatial relationship could be the geometrical configuration which the two robot end-effectors are required to maintain to perform a task collaboratively. In the previous system, the user directly controls two simple 3 degree-of-freedom (DoF) robots, which is not realistic for a MIS procedure. The main

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contribution of this paper is to extend the multi-robot control by including master-slave pairs, where a *slave* robot relates to a *master* manipulator by teleoperator constraints, in addition to multi-robot collaborative constraints for the slave robots.

The paper is organized as follows: section II describes the formulation of the master-slave robot teleoperation as a constrained optimization problem, section III demonstrates the algorithm's ability to provide surgeons with cooperative assistance for a complex bimanual task (knot positioning) and section IV describes the implementation on the customized da Vinci Surgical system, followed by description of the interactive virtual reality simulation environment and experiment protocols.

II. CONSTRAINED CONTROL FOR MULTI-ROBOT TELEOPERATION

A. Constrained Optimization Based Teleoperation

The da Vinci Surgical System[®], from Intuitive Surgical, Inc. is a commercially available and clinically approved telerobotic system for MIS [6]. In a typical MIS procedure, the surgeon operates two Master Tele-Manipulators (MTM) to control any of three Patient Side Manipulators (PSM) without intelligent assistance and with minimal haptic feedback from the robot system. Through a collaboration agreement, we have acquired the mechanical subsystem, which includes two MTM/PSM pairs and a viewing console. Each MTM is a cable driven 7-DoF serial robot with a redundant wrist mechanism. The PSM is kinematically different, and can mount a series of 3-DoF interchangeable EndoWrist[™] end-effector tools. We are using custom motion controllers and software, based on our real-time robotic control library, *cisst*, and the *Surgical Assistant Workstation* software framework [7].

An overview of the constrained optimization based teleoperation is shown in Figure 2. Subscripts m and s are used for master and slave respectively.

Fig. 1. Master Controller

In Figure 1, we model the master manipulator as a kinematic device with position $p_m \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and orientation given by matrix $R_m \in SO(3)$. The actual robot frame $F_m = [R_m | p_m]$ is computed using forward kinematics and joint position q_m . For impedance-type robots, under quasi-static conditions, the user input force f_{user} , can be approximated by the Cartesian position and orientation errors as $p_m^e = p_m^c - p_m$ and $R_m^e = R_m^c \cdot R_m^{-1}$ [8]. Using Rodrigues' formula, we extract twist coordinates of R_m^e to

get $(\theta_m \cdot \omega_m)$, where ω_m is the unit vector of the axis of rotation. The desired incremental motion, ΔX_m^d , a six vector, is $[p_m^e | (\theta_m \cdot \omega_m)]$. The constrained optimization block solves the incremental joint motion, \dot{q}_m , and has an objective requiring the incremental motion of the master to be as close as possible to ΔX_m^d , subject to constraints on joint range and velocity limits (see Table I). If the incremental motions are sufficiently small for each iteration, then, $\Delta X_m / \Delta t = J_m \Delta q_m / \Delta t$ approximates $\dot{X}_m = J_m \dot{q}_m$, where J_m is the manipulator Jacobian, and Δt is the period of the control loop. Individual joints are servoed to commanded set points q_m^c by low-level Proportional-Derivative (PD) controllers.

Fig. 2. Teleoperation Control Algorithm Overview. Subscripts m and s are used for master and slave respectively, and l and r denote left or right teleoperator pair

For teleoperation, the desired frame of the slave, F_s^d , is a linear transformation (offset and scaling) of the master's frame F_m^c . The desired incremental motion for the slave, ΔX_s^d , is computed similarly by using F_s^d and F_s , and is equal to $[p_s^e | (\theta_s \cdot \omega_s)]$. For pure teleoperated tasks (i.e., without the collaborative controller), ΔX_s^d would be passed to the slave controller block, where a slave constrained optimization similar to that of the master's is performed. Not shown in Figure 2 is the *feedback objective* (Table I, line 2), which is used to implement bilateral teleoperation feedback. When the slave encounters a force in the environment, (e.g, obstacle), it lags behind the command position and the user haptically feels this resistance, as the *feedback objective* acts to minimize the master/slave tracking error, $\Delta X_{m,s}^e$, by opposing the user's input motion.

TABLE I
THE TELEOPERATION OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Objective	Master	$\min_{\Delta q_m} \ \Delta X_m - \Delta X_m^d\ $
Objective	Feedback	$\min_{\Delta q_m} \ \Delta X_m - \Delta X_{m,s}^e\ $
Constraint	Joint Limit	$q_L < q_m < q_U$
Constraint	Joint Velocity Limit	$\dot{q}_m < \dot{q}_U$

B. Multi-Robot Collaborative Control

A collaborative controller uses *correspondence constraints* that relate to multiple robots operating in the task. The inputs to this collaborative controller are multiple slave desired incremental Cartesian motions ΔX_s^d , and the outputs are expected incremental Cartesian motions for the individual slave robots, ΔX_s^{d*} , denoted by *. These constraints will be explained in section III-B.

III. KNOT POSITIONING TASK

Knot tying is a bimanual task requiring dexterous two-handed manipulation. Although knot tying is complex, here we focus on the subtask of knot positioning. The knot positioning task begins once the suture is passed through the tissue and the free ends of suture are looped around each other. The task involves controlling the magnitude and the direction of motion of the two free ends of the thread to position the knot on the tissue, see Figure 3. Previous work in [5] has demonstrated that in a set-up with simple 3DoF admittance-type force controlled robots, with the help of motion constraints, it is possible to obtain reasonable positioning of the knot, even with a single hand. It is the purpose of this paper to extend this type of multi-robot constrained motion framework to a realistic teleoperated setup, e.g., the da Vinci system, and then evaluate the efficacy of the framework in a clinically relevant setting.

A. Kinematics of Knot Positioning

To create a simplified knot motion model for real-time control, we made a few simplifications, as seen in the half-square knot in Figure 3: (1) a knot is made up of four intersecting lines with negligible slack, (2) the length of the two ends of the thread that loop around each other is negligible, (3) the fixed ends, E_1 and E_2 , are known and fixed with respect to the knot coordinate frame and (4) the knot is a planar knot in the XY plane. The knot position is K . F_1 and F_2 correspond to the free ends of the thread and are attached to the slave end-effectors. β_1 and β_2 are the angles between the the free sections and the horizontal.

Fig. 3. Knot positioning task illustration. Subscripts s denote values at start of task

We present the “knot jacobians” J_{kf} and J_{bf} , in Eq. 2, to estimate the incremental motion of the knot position, $[\dot{K}_x, \dot{K}_y]$ and the beta angles, $[\dot{\beta}_1, \dot{\beta}_2]$, given the current geometry of the knot in terms of F_i , K , and E_i and incremental motion of the free ends, \dot{F}_1 and \dot{F}_2 . This relationship must be maintained in the multi-robot collaborative controller.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{K}_x \\ \dot{K}_y \\ \dot{\beta}_1 \\ \dot{\beta}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{kf} \\ J_{bf} \end{bmatrix} (F_i, K, E_i) \begin{bmatrix} \dot{F}_{1x} \\ \dot{F}_{1y} \\ \dot{F}_{2x} \\ \dot{F}_{2y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

B. Multi-Robot Correspondence Constraints

Motion constraints are applied in the multi-robot constrained optimization controller to assist the user to teleoperate the two slave end-effectors such that the knot moves along the desired direction. The optimization objective functions specify that the incremental Cartesian output and desired input motion are closely matched for both Slave robots. The constraints are: (1) maintain the thread angles β_i within a range $[\beta_L, \beta_U]$ such that the friction is low enough for threads to slide across, (2) move the knot along the desired direction along line L , and (3) no reverse motion, from knot starting location, K_s , to the desired end position, K_d . If the knot moves backwards, the threads might not be taut and the assumption of the straight threads intersecting at the knot will be invalid. These are correspondence constraints, because the left and right slave motions are coupled through these constraints. At each control step, the controller solves for $\Delta X_{s,l}^{d*}, \Delta X_{s,r}^{d*}$, subject to the objectives and constraints in Table II, subscript i denotes left or right. $\Delta X_{s,l}^{d*}$ and $\Delta X_{s,r}^{d*}$ are equivalent to \dot{F}_1 , and \dot{F}_2 , respectively, because the free ends of the thread are held by the end-effectors of the slaves. ϵ represents the tolerance for each constraint. For details of the derivation of the constraints, see [5].

TABLE II
MULTI-ROBOT CONTROLLER

Objective	Motion Tracking	$\min \ \Delta X_{s,i}^d - \Delta X_{s,i}^{d*}\ $
Constraint	Sliding Condition	$\beta_L \leq J_{bf}^T \cdot \Delta X_{s,i}^{d*} + \beta \leq \beta_U$
Constraint	Move Along Direction	$\ \delta_p + \Delta X_{s,i}^{d*}\ \leq \epsilon$
Constraint	Do Not Move Backwards	$-J_k^T \cdot \Delta X_{s,i}^{d*} \leq \epsilon$

C. Theoretical Simulation Results

In the simulation tests, we define a desired knot position trajectory, which is the line joining the knot’s starting position, K_s and end, K_d , at the center of the two fixed ends of the thread, E_1 and E_2 . At each control step, given a desired velocity at the free ends, the multi-robot constraint controller computes the expected free end velocities, \dot{F}_1 and \dot{F}_2 , such that the knot moves along the desired trajectory, as well as the incremental motion of the knot state, i.e., knot position, K and beta angles, β_1 and β_2 . Figure 4 shows the four segments that form the knot and successive motion of these

segments and the knot. We record the errors (in millimeters), between successive knot positions K , and the projection of this position along this trajectory and the mean, maximum and standard deviation of the absolute value of the errors.

Fig. 4. Knot positioning task simulation

We assume that the determination of the knot position through image processing is accurate, but this is certainly not the case. Unfortunately, it is difficult to establish a ground truth for knot position and quantify this error. To better understand the effect of uncertainty in knot position determination, we ran the simulation with random uniform noise in knot measurement at each control step, at 0.1 mm, 0.5 mm and 1.0 mm and observed that the main cause of knot trajectory tracking error is due to errors in knot position determination, see Table III. The maximum knot trajectory tracking errors are at the same magnitude as knot position errors. We believe that the accuracy and robustness of the system can be increased by enhancing the vision component of the system.

TABLE III
KNOT TRAJECTORY TRACKING ERRORS IN MM

Noise	Max	Mea	St. Dev.
0	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.1	0.13	0.08	0.05
0.5	0.67	0.50	0.20
1.0	1.29	0.81	0.43

Figure 5 shows the magnitudes of the desired incremental motions as compared to the optimized incremental motions, for the left and right free ends respectively. The magnitudes of the desired incremental motion are constant, at 1.2748 mm and 1.0 mm respectively. We observe that the multi-robot constraint controller speeds up or slows down the optimized incremental motion of the free ends in order for the knot to move along the desired trajectory within a tolerance ϵ .

Fig. 5. Magnitude of desired incremental motion vs. optimized incremental motion for left and right slaves

Fig. 6. Knot positioning experiment setup. Two MTMs are mounted below the surgeon's Viewer Console. Two PSMs hold the knot threads. The SVS stereo-camera system is from Videre Design. (Master image courtesy of Intuitive Surgical, Inc.)

IV. IMPLEMENTATION ON THE DA VINCI ROBOT

A. System Architecture

In the knot positioning task, the user teleoperates the slave end-effectors via the master manipulators. For each control step, user input motion at each master, with configuration, F_m^c , is sent to the corresponding slave, and the slave computes, ΔX_s^d , the desired incremental Cartesian motion. The ΔX_s^d from both slaves are then passed to the multi-robot optimization controller, along with the knot position. The multi-robot controller takes into account knot positioning constraints and objectives (see Table II), and computes the expected incremental Cartesian motions, ΔX_s^{d*} for left and right slave controllers. Individual joint-level constrained optimization in each master and slave controller computes the incremental joint motion, Δq_s , and sends the desired joint positions to the servo thread, which implements Proportional-Derivative (PD) feedback control and gravity compensation (for masters only), and sends torque to each motor controller.

Fig. 7. Software block diagram and data flow

The image processing program tracks the knot position for successive frames. The knot thread is made of bright colored fishing line instead of a typical dark colored suture thread. Existing color segmentation algorithms are used to segment the knot into four segments, and each segment is approximated by a straight line. The approximation keeps the results sufficiently accurate because the thread is mostly taut for the duration of the experiment. The knot position is given by the intersection of the four thread segments. This processing is repeated for both left and right stereo image streams. A standard stereo-reconstruction technique is used to compute the 3D position from the 2D knot position projections.

Each master/slave pair is controlled on a single workstation and the left and right pairs are connected through a communication network. These distributed threads operate at different rates, ranging from 1 KHz for the PD control threads to 100 Hz for the master/slave control threads, and to the computer vision thread, which operates at below 20 Hz. Note that while the video is captured and buffered at a higher frame rate (around 30 Hz), it is only processed at about 20 Hz. Implementing a real-time, multi-rate, asynchronous distributed control system is a significant engineering effort. We make use of the *cisst* library, which provides real-time control, safe and uniform inter-thread and inter-process communication, vector/matrix computation and computer vision processing [9].

B. Calibration and Coordinate Transformations

Figure 8 shows the transformations between various coordinate frames of reference. It is essential to determine and continually update these transformations in order to transform various inputs into a common frame of reference, (e.g., the knot frame) for the multi-robot constrained optimization computation.

T_{tl}^{sl} is the transformation between the end-effector frame and the base frame of the left slave. Similarly, T_{tr}^{sr} is for the right slave. These are computed from the forward kinematics, *fwd_kin*.

T_c^{sl} is the transformation between the slave left base and camera frame. First, we compute the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of the stereo-camera system, using the Camera Calibration Toolbox for Matlab [10]. Then, using these parameters, we triangulate 3D points in the camera

space. To compute T_c^{sl} , we attach a modified da Vinci EndoWristTM tool with fiducials to the end-effector of the slave and use an $AX = XB$ calibration technique outlined in [11].

T_c^k is the transformation between the knot base and camera. By touching a few points on the knot platform with the end-effector, we obtained the coordinates of the same points in both the slave frame and the camera, and using this correspondence, we determine the transformation using rigid body registration.

Fig. 8. $\{c\}$ is camera coordinate frame. The left and right slave base frames are $\{sl\}$ and $\{sr\}$, and end-effector frames are $\{tl\}$ and $\{tr\}$. The knot base coordinate frame is denoted by $\{k\}$.

The multi-robot optimization block inputs are Cartesian incremental slave motion, ΔX_s^d and knot center position, K . We can multiply the transformations determined from the calibration process to transform these into the knot base frame, see Equations (3), (4).

$$\Delta F_k = T_c^k \times T_{sl}^c \times T_{tl}^{sl} \times \Delta X_s^d \quad (3)$$

$$K_k = T_c^k \times K \quad (4)$$

V. INTERACTIVE SIMULATION AND SYSTEM VERIFICATION

We have created an interactive virtual reality simulation environment, using the OpenSceneGraph package, for the verification of the multi-robot optimization controller logic. This eliminates the need for determining the transformations between various coordinate frames of references. In addition, we simulate the incremental knot kinematics to avoid computer vision based knot tracking. In this case, the slaves arms and knot are replaced by their respective virtual graphical models in a 3D environment that the user can view, through the daVinci Viewer Console.

During the interactive simulation, user manipulates the two masters, which generates desired incremental Cartesian motion, ΔX_s^d , for the left and right slave, respectively. The ΔX_s^d for both slaves are passed to the multi-robot optimization controller, which takes into account simulated knot position, and knot positioning constraints and objectives, and computes the expected incremental Cartesian motion,

ΔX_s^{d*} for both slaves. The simulator also computes the incremental knot position and updates the knot position and the slave positions for the next iteration. Note that bilateral teleoperation feedback can be enabled based on the virtual slave position. Under the assumption of ideal knot behavior, the iterative simulation can be used to conduct the experimental protocol described below.

Fig. 9. Interactive Virtual Reality Simulation

VI. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOLS

Three experiment protocols are devised to determine the efficacy of using robot assistance in knot positioning.

- (a) No assistance mode: The user telemanipulates knot through masters without any motion constraints. The user carefully moves the PSMs such that the knot moves along the desired trajectory.
- (b) Two-Handed assistance mode: The user telemanipulates knot through masters with the motion constraints. We also examine the effect on accuracy and user experience by varying the haptic force feedback gain between the master and slave.
- (c) Follower assistance mode: The user operates the master using his or her dominant hand. Due to knot positioning objectives and constraints, the slave not being manipulated by the user follows the robot being held by the user to ensure these constraints are met.

Experiments can be conducted on the interactive simulation (with simulated knot tracking) and the full system, which includes image processing based knot tracking. In both cases, all test subjects are asked to manipulate the masters from the surgical viewing console and perform the task of moving the ends of the thread held by the slaves (real or virtual) as accurately as possible. We will record the knot trajectory tracking errors between successive knot positions K , and the projection of this position along this trajectory and the time required to complete the task in each of the trials. The total time is measured from the moment the user starts to move the knot until the user has completed moving the knot by a fixed distance. We are interested in examining the task completion time in manual operation or robotic assistance mode. At this

time, the experiments with the full system have yet to be completed.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have developed a multi-robot collaborative telerobotic system suitable for MIS procedures. Surgeons performing MIS procedures must deal with a constrained working environment, with long instruments and awkward angles. Cooperative control that combines a surgeon's input with motion assistance based on intra-operative sensing can be helpful especially when multiple robots are being controlled. We believe that robotic assistance will result in significant reduction in the average error from the desired trajectory. We will validate our hypothesis through subject trials on the robotic assisted knot positioning task.

We plan to expand to other MIS surgical tasks, or other telemanipulation tasks that require two or more collaborating robots. The da Vinci Surgical System can have up to three slaves for surgical manipulation. It would be beneficial if the surgeon could perform some critical task with his/her dominant hand, while his/her non-dominant hand performs a routine task such as knot tying and the *intelligent* controller moves the third arm to perform complex manipulation to assist in completing the knot task.

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